

MODERN TURKISH AND UZBEKI STORIES: TYPOLOGY AND INFLUENCE

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Abstract: In this article, in a period of developing literary, political, cultural and economic relations between the Turkish and Uzbek peoples, it is important to compare their literary trends, currents, and the lives of creators. Also, the study of typology in Turkish and Uzbek stories is of great importance today.

Key words: Turkish and Uzbek stories, literary influence, typology, comparative study, typological approach, typological analysis.

Introduction:

Comparative analysis of modern linguistics. The similar features of Turkish and Uzbek linguistics. The study and analysis of linguistic structures in it is one of the important tasks for today's linguistics. Therefore, we try to analyze the typological features of Turkish and Uzbek language linguistics during our scientific activity.

Before thinking about typology, let's get fully acquainted. Topology (type and ...logy) is a method of scientific classification of objects using abstract, generalized models (types). The most important structural (structural) and functional features of the studied objects are noted. The main feature of typology is that it allows not only to classify the objects that have been studied, but also to show (determine) the existence of objects that are not yet known to the science of this or that period (for example, D.I. Mendeleev's periodic system of elements). Typology, one of the universal methods of scientific thinking, is based on revealing the similarities and differences between the studied objects, finding ways to compare and equate them, and is used in many fields of science, but biology, which has many objects with different characteristics. it is effectively used in such subjects as chemistry, geography, linguistics, and psychology.

In linguistics, typology is a branch of linguistics that identifies and summarizes the important features of the structure of the language in general, based on the study of the construction of some derived languages and their comprehensive comparison. Typological methods are aimed at identifying similarities and differences based on the phonology, morphology, syntax and lexis of different regional languages, defining linguistic universals, as well as types of languages - generalized, perfect concepts about the nature of language construction. The types of languages are determined by the way concepts are expressed in grammar, the technique of expressing relationships, and the degree of connection. Typological studies are also conducted on the basis of separate, some sub-systems of the language system, due to which phonological, morphological, syntactic and semantic typologies are distinguished. Comparative typology studies some features of two or more cognate or non-cognate languages of different systems. Identifiable typological signs reflect the specific

characteristics of a certain subsystem, but in the construction of the language, they are combined in different proportions, so one of these signs is the main, leading one.

The typological study of literature consists in the fact that it includes the comparison of literary phenomena as a starting point for scientific analysis.

Typology is the study of types of things, or the systematic classification of types according to their common characteristics.

Typology implies the discovery of common or similar development trends in the literature of peoples whose language and historical fate are close, and in the literature of peoples whose language and historical fate are far from each other¹.

M.B. Khrapchenko writes: "The typological study of literature is not about the individuality of literary phenomena and their similar characteristics and interdependence, but about a well-known literary-aesthetic community, a certain phenomenon of a certain is to reveal the principles and principles that allow us to talk about the belonging to the species and gender"².

As is customary nowadays, there are different levels of typological studies. Along with the typology of literary trends, the typology of genres is of great importance. Especially in art criticism, the typology of style is rapidly developing. In school literature, the typology of language images and figurative and expressive means characteristic of a certain literary trend or genre is the most interesting. This level of research is available to students and allows them to draw their own conclusions by comparing different literary phenomena.

The typological approach not only helps to establish connections between different literary works and their authors, but also allows generalization. Such an approach allows not only to understand the work of a particular writer, but also to show it in the literary context of that time, to put it on a par with other Turkish and foreign writers, and to reveal the writer's commonality. to see creative individuality against the background of literary and worldview positions and common moments of different authors.

The use of a typological approach makes learning problematic, develops, helps students to solve their tasks. At the same time, an atmosphere of research, creativity, and cooperation is created between the students and the teacher in the literature classes. The teacher's role in this is to guide, advise and, most importantly, set the task. A well-structured problem gives students a clear idea of what they need to do and what they can do to solve it.

Such classroom work should, of course, be done after studying the works of the writers to be compared. By proposing specific works for analysis, repeating what has been previously learned at the same time allows students to see the development of the literary process, to understand the laws of the continuity of this development, which allows students to have a holistic perception of literature.

Identifying the similarities and differences in the authors' creative positions, characters, methods of creating images, using compositional tools, determining the genre specificity of the works, what works can be suggested for typological study. A morphological (typological) classification of languages was created based on the structural structure of the word, but it

¹ Uzbek literature in the aspect of comparative literary studies: influence and typology. Tashkent "Muharrir Nashriyoti" 2013. Bakhtiyor Nazarov Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, academician. 6- p.

² Typological approach to the study of literary phenomena. S. V. Anatolyeva. "Festival of Pedagogical Ideas" distance course for teachers. 2020.-4- p.

has not been proven that the types of languages meet in a pure form, as the type of language may change as a result of gradual development. Typological studies in the field of linguistics began with the works of the German scientist F. Schlegel. Later, German scientists on language typology A.V. Schlegel, V. Humboldt, H. Steinthal, A. Schleicher, American E. Sepir, Czech V. Skalichka, French A. Martine, Turks F.F. Fortunatov, I.I. Meshchaninov, B. Uspensky, Yu.V. .Rozhdestvensky, V.N. Yarseva and others who conducted research. A. Abduazizov, J. Boronov, Q. Toymetov and others are also in Uzbekistan. Those who dealt with issues of typology.

The lexicon of the Uzbek and Turkish languages differs, first of all, by the fact that these languages belong to genetically different families. Although the Uzbek language is typologically included among all agglutinative languages by many scientists in the family of Altaic languages, genetically it belongs to the group of Turkic languages that form a separate family. The basis of the vocabulary of our language is common Turkic and Uzbek words. It should be said that the Turkish language, both typologically and genetically, belongs to the Slavic group of the Indo-European language family, which is based on Pan-Slavic and Old Turkish words. During the historical development of the lexicon of both languages, they have experienced various events, and their lexical composition is made up of words borrowed from different languages. For example, there are many Persian-Tajik and Arabic words in the Uzbek language, and there are only a few words borrowed from the Turkish language. The lexicon of the Uzbek language is mainly:

1. general Turkish words;
2. Uzbek words;
3. Arabic words;
4. Persian-Tajik words;
5. It consists of layers like possessive words.

Literature Analysis and Methods:

The book "Comparative grammar of Uzbek and Turkish languages" by Azizov O. Safaev A. Jamolkhanov and. T., Kissen's study guide was used. Also, in clarifying morphological, phonetic, semantic differences, Mahmudov N., Nurmonov A.'s "Theoretical grammar of the Uzbek language", Rahmatullaev Sh. The literature "Comparison of Uzbek and Turkish languages" and "Grammar of the Turkish language" by Reshetov V.V. and Reshetova were studied. Accordingly, historical-genetic, socio-cultural, lexical-semantic, component, contextual, cognitive-discursive, and statistical methods of analysis were used during the research of the article.

Results and discussion:

Turkish words that entered the Uzbek language in historical times, that is, until the beginning of the 20th century, underwent certain phonetic changes and became Uzbek, so they do not differ from the original Uzbek words in terms of pronunciation, and in writing is expressed in a way that corresponds to the pronunciation. A number of new words were also created in Uzbek language by adding suffixes based on native words. The phonetic and orthographic features of such words also correspond to the norms of the Turkish language.

The lexical structure of the Turkish language also includes Uzbek, Forstogic, and Arabic words, almost all of which have undergone phonetic changes, so there is a difference between the pronunciation and writing of such words in the Uzbek and Turkish languages. differences are visible.

As semantic differences, there are cases of meaning narrowing, expansion or change in Uzbek loanwords. For example, the word "pen" in Turkish has three meanings, such as kolcha (small hand), handle, writing instrument, and in Uzbek, this word is used only in the sense of a writing instrument. The word kartmon (karman, i.e. pocket) borrowed from the Turkish language has withdrawn from its true meaning in the Turkish language and acquired a completely different meaning in the Uzbek language (a money bag). , the word samovar, in addition to the meaning of a teapot in Turkish, has an additional meaning in Uzbek - a teahouse. The meanings of Uzbek and Turkish words do not always match in terms of quantity in both languages. For example, the Uzbek word okimak means both "to study" and "to learn".

In general, the feature of polysemy is characteristic of words in both languages, and most of them belong to the oldest lexical layers in both Uzbek and Turkish languages. In some cases, the initial and derivative meanings of polysemantic words in Uzbek correspond exactly to Turkish ones. The words "gold" and "iron" in the cited examples have retained their original and derived meanings in the compounds translated from Turkish to Uzbek. However, such a situation does not always appear in translation. Sometimes the main lexical meanings of the words expressing the same concept are the same in Uzbek and Turkish standards, but the new meanings created from them are completely incompatible in the two languages. For example, in the Uzbek language, the handle of a pot is shaped like an ear, so this concept is also called an ear in the Uzbek language.

Therefore, when comparing the lexicon of the Turkish and Uzbek languages, it is appropriate to use larger units, more precisely, sentences and texts, rather than words. It is known that folk oral creativity is passed down from ancestors to generations, it lives for centuries, improves, expands and becomes richer. The Uzbek language is rich in various expressions, proverbs and fixed combinations, which express the history, culture, traditions and spirituality of our people.

We call the lexical units that are composed of two or more words and express a single meaning, phrases or phraseologisms or phraseological units. Usually, phrases are evaluated as units whose meaning is equal to a word (lexema). It is true that the units that combine to form a stable combination, i.e., a phrase, basically express a single meaning, a single concept, but there are more colors and exaggerations than in a lexeme. Therefore, the lexical meaning cannot be equal to the phraseological meaning. Otherwise, we would not be using expressions to express a concept.

As in all languages, the lexical structure of the Turkish language also contains expressions, which are used in speech with different meanings and colors.

When comparing the structure and composition of phrases in the Uzbek and Turkish languages, it is determined that there are the following similarities between them. When the phraseologisms in the Uzbek and Turkish languages are semantically compared, the following situations are revealed. The research shows that, according to the latest statistical data, the words borrowed from the Turkish language and through this language from other languages in the modern Uzbek literary language are about 30%. Turkish international words in the lexicon of our language are used as active words both in scientific and technical literature and in oral speech. It was found that there are certain differences between native words and words in the Turkish language.

Comparative typology includes directions such as characterology and universal grammar. Both of these directions deal with the comparison of languages. However, there are also differences between them: characterology compares only the same layers in languages, while universal grammar takes into account lexical tools in addition to grammatical tools when comparing languages. According to scientist M. Iriskulov, the plural category includes the following tools from the point of view of universal grammar:

- 1. Adverbs forming the plural form.**
- 2. Words belonging to the number group.**
- 3. Some pronouns.**
- 4. Collective nouns.**
- 5. Phonetic phenomena that change word forms (for example, in inflectional languages).**

Universal grammar is useful for comparing unrelated language systems. It also creates a very important foundation for translation theory, lexicography, and methodological sciences. In addition, linguistic system evidence obtained as a result of comparative typological studies is used to create language universals and general typological law. Comparative typology is not only based on the similarities in the language system, but also studies the differences in the system units and inter-layer differences in the expression of certain categorical meanings.

It is known that the Uzbek language belongs to the Turkic group of the Altaic language family, and typologically it belongs to the group of agglutinative languages. The Turkish language belongs to the Slavic group of the Indo-European language family, which is considered the largest family in the world, and according to the typological classification, it is considered an inflectional language.

"Comparative typology of Uzbek and Turkish languages" is one of the main subjects for philological majors. This science is a science about issues such as the inherent nature of the Uzbek and Turkish languages, the laws of construction, the methodology and methods of comparing and contrasting them, and the identification of similarities and differences between the systems of the Uzbek and Turkish languages. The main goal of the science is to provide knowledge about comparative typology, agglutinative and inflectional languages, their construction laws, commonalities and specifics between them, comparing and comparing them.

"Comparative typology of the Uzbek and Turkish languages" sets the task of providing information about the following subordinated to the main goal:

- **general information about comparative typology;**
- **specific features of agglutinative and inflectional languages;**
- **methodology of comparative language learning;**
- **comparative study of phonemes characteristic of two languages;**
- **comparative study of the vocabulary of the Uzbek and Turkish languages;**
- **to identify the differences regarding the morphological level of languages;**
- **to identify syntactic commonalities and peculiarities between languages using comparison.**

Learning and describing the language is done with different methods and techniques. For example, the course "Current Uzbek Literary Language" is considered an example of describing a language. In this case, the characteristics of the Uzbek language, its construction laws, are described only on the example of one language, that is, the Uzbek language. This

study of language is called private linguistics. Comparative typology is one of the components of general linguistics, in which the commonalities between languages and the specific characteristics, similarities and differences of each language are studied, and the value of languages is determined.

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